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Normative scenario script for a workshop on land degradation

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The workshop script was used to explore land degradation from the perspective of local people from the Țârnava Mare (TM) microregion. Implemented as a normative scenario workshop, it facilitated community engagement to envision desirable futures and co-develop strategies for sustainable land management.

To increase text clarity and help readers navigate the script's structure, color coding is used. Each color highlights a different type of content, according to the Legend below.

Legend: **Blue** – Main questions that were directly asked to participants; **Brown** – Instructions or tasks for facilitators; **Green** – Probing/Follow-up questions to help participants reflect more deeply.

PART 1 – INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT SETTING

Welcome from the facilitators & presentation of the workshop agenda

Purpose of the meeting: Why are we here? Why this area? What is land degradation?

A ten-minute presentation on the critical importance of healthy soil for sustainable agriculture and climate resilience was run. It demonstrated how traditional land-use practices can enhance soil quality, increase productivity, and contribute to carbon sequestration.

Workshop objective:

To co-create a shared vision for a sustainable, resilient, and ecologically restored Târnava Mare microregion by 2050. Together, we can identify concrete steps, effective strategies, and key partnerships to bring this vision to life.

- **Introduction to normative scenario planning:**

"We are not just asking what could happen, but what *should happen and how we can make this vision a reality*".

Explanations about the definition of the term "land" as used in the workshop were provided. Land includes the following categories (according to Art. 2 of Law 18/1991, points a-e): agricultural land (arable, vineyards, orchards, pastures, meadows), forests and other land with forest vegetation (including degraded land designated for afforestation), land with water resources, intra-urban land (within urban and rural settlements, where buildings and other infrastructures are located, including agricultural and forest land), land with special use (roads, railways, etc.)

- **Icebreaker activity: "I say one, you say two"**

1.1 Can you think of 2–3 words that, in your opinion, best describe TM as it is today?

Photo elicitation activity: Two contrasting images of degraded and restored landscapes are presented to the participants.

Discussion:

1.2 Looking towards the future: Which image most accurately represents how you would like the TM microregion to look in 2050? Why?

For facilitators: Kindly invite participants who wish to also write or draw the answer to question 1.1 on a piece of paper.

PART 2 – DEFINING THE CORE PROBLEM

2.1 What does land degradation mean to you?

Please provide some examples of specific locations within the TM microregion exhibiting signs of land degradation.

Table 1

2.2 How would you describe the current state of the previously defined land types and their associated ecosystems* within the TM microregion?			
Current state of land	Severely degraded		
2.3 How would you describe the land use and ecosystems in the Târnava Mare microregion?			
Land use patterns**	Intensive use occurs when economic interests are prioritized, resulting in harm to nature.		

* Examples of ecosystems in the TM microregion: Natural grasslands, forests, wetlands (rivers), agricultural ecosystems (cultivated land functioning as a human-modified ecological system), degraded ecosystems (areas where the natural balance has been severely affected). A healthy ecosystem means fertile soil, clean water, biodiversity (a variety of species), and functional ecosystem services (e.g., pollination, water retention, protection against erosion). In this context, ecosystems refer to the natural environment (e.g., plants, animals, soil, water) and how these elements work together to sustain life.

** Land use refers to how people manage and utilize land for various social, economic, and cultural activities. Concrete examples of land use: agriculture (crop farming, orchards, gardens), grazing (for livestock), forestry (forest exploitation), construction (houses, infrastructure), tourism (designated visitor areas), protected/conservation areas (nature reserves), or fallow land. In essence, we refer to how the community utilizes the available land, specifically, how it is divided, used, and whether these practices are sustainable or not.

2.4 Do you think land degradation is an urgent issue (from an ecological, social, or economic perspective)? Why?

2.5 What are the leading causes of land degradation? (E.g., overgrazing, erosion, tourism pressure, and the impact of climate change).

Table 2

CAUSES OF LAND DEGRADATION	SEVERITY (LOW / MEDIUM / HIGH	MAIN AFFECTED AREAS (<i>slopes, communal pastures, agricultural land, hillsides, the entire region, natural attractions, forests, river</i>)	ENVIRON MENTAL IMPACT	ECONOMIC IMPACT	SOCIAL IMPACT	INTERACTIONS BETWEEN THE CAUSES FROM COLUMN 1 <i>(for example: climate variability worsens vegetation loss, links to overgrazing and deforestation, amplifies all other causes, etc.)</i>
1 Intensive grazing						
2 Soil erosion						
3 Tourism pressure (e.g., off-road activities/competition)						
4 Climatic conditions (wind, rain, drought, extreme temperatures, etc.)						
5 Deforestation						
6 Intensive agriculture						
7 Unsustainable agricultural practices (e.g., lack of crop rotation, improper plowing, etc.)						
8 Construction and urbanization						
9 Construction and operation of factories (industrial facilities)						
10 Agricultural pollution						
11 Industrial pollution						
12 Waste pollution						
13 Irrigation (too much, too little)						
14 Other causes (Please mention)						

2.6 Please vote for the top 3 causes of land degradation

 Facilitators write the top 3 causes on an A3 sheet of paper.

PART 3 – ENVISIONING A DESIRED FUTURE (2050)

Guided future-visioning exercise:

3.1 Imagine you are walking through the TM microregion in the year 2050.

3.1a. What do you see, hear, and feel?

3.1b. What kind of landscape is there?

3.1c. What does the soil look like?

3.1d. Are the hills green or barren?

3.1e. Who lives here, and what do they do?

3.1f. What types of activities are taking place? (Agriculture, tourism, conservation activities, etc.)

Participants are invited to summarize THEIR DESIRED VISION FOR 2050 based on the ideas expressed by the majority. We pay attention to quantification in terms of deficit/excess (e.g., 10%, one quarter, etc.). Outcome: A co-created vision statement including values and indicators of success.

 Draft a description of the imagined (desired) future for 2050 (5–10 lines). This will be written on an A4 sheet of paper and then validated by the participants.

Table 3

Causes	<i>Decision/Intervention</i> 3.2 Decision/Intervention area for the three leading causes identified in PART 2*	<i>Tarde-offs</i> 3.3 What trade-offs had to be made to eliminate each of these causes to reach the desired future in 2050?**	<i>Difficulties</i> 3.4 What difficult decisions might communities face during this transition toward 2050 when trying to eliminate each cause?***	<i>Affected actors</i> 3.5 Who would be affected – both if the cause persists and if it is eliminated?****
For cause 1				
For cause 2				
For cause 3				
	*E.g., Obtaining external funding (from outside the community) for various projects	** E.g., Conversion of agricultural land into forest corridors	***E.g., Balancing the community’s autonomy and decision-making power with the need to rely on external support	****E.g., Subsistence farmers

Facilitators: Take the A3 sheet of paper from Part 2, question 2.6, and show it to the participants to refresh their memories.

PART 4 – BACKCASTING TIMELINE (USING STEEP)

Creating a chronological timeline backward from 2050 to the present (2026)

Tabel 4

 Social dimension (Values, norms, behaviors, community cooperation, social innovation)	4.1.a Social changes needed What changes in the community or in habits need to take place at this stage to reach the desired vision by 2050?	4.2.a Social changes needed What changes in the community or in habits need to take place at this stage to reach the desired vision by 2050?	4.3.a Social changes needed What changes in the community or in habits need to take place at this stage to reach the desired vision by 2050?
 Technological dimension (Tools, innovation, know-how, technology)	4.1.b Necessary technologies What tools (technologies) need to be adopted at this stage to achieve the desired 2050 vision?	4.2.b Necessary technologies What tools (technologies) should be implemented at this stage to help realize the 2050 vision?	4.3.b Necessary technologies What tools (technologies) must be adopted at this stage to ensure the 2050 vision becomes a reality?

<p>Economic dimension (Financial incentives, livelihoods, investments)</p>	<p>4.1.c Economic levers What investments or programs need to be implemented at this stage to achieve the desired 2050 vision?</p>	<p>4.2.c Economic levers What investments or programs should be adopted at this stage to help realize the desired 2050 vision?</p>	<p>4.3.c Economic levers What investments or programs are required at this stage to enable the realization of the 2050 vision?</p>
<p>Environmental dimension (land, water, air, biodiversity)</p>	<p>4.1.d Environmental measures/interventions What visible environmental impacts/changes appear at this stage because of the measures taken to achieve the 2050 vision? (positive)</p>	<p>4.2.d Environmental measures/interventions What visible environmental impacts/changes occur at this stage because of the actions taken to achieve the 2050 vision? (positive)</p>	<p>4.3.d Environmental measures/interventions What visible environmental impacts/changes occur at this stage to ensure the achievement of the 2050 vision? (positive)</p>
<p>Political dimension (legislation, institutions, policies, actors, balance of power)</p>	<p>4.1.e Political actions What policies (measures, strategies) and legislation need to be implemented at this stage to support the achievement of the desired 2050 vision?</p>	<p>4.2.e Political actions What policies (measures, strategies) and legislation need to be implemented at this stage to advance progress toward the 2050 vision?</p>	<p>4.3.e Political actions What policies (measures, strategies) and legislation need to be implemented at this stage to drive progress toward the achievement of the 2050 vision?</p>

**PART 5 – ANALYSIS OF ENABLING FACTORS AND CONSTRAINTS
in achieving the desired 2050 vision**

Tabel 5

Dimension	Internal (within the community/system)	External (external forces beyond local control)
Enabling factors (for achieving the 2050 vision)		
Constraints (obstacles to achieving the 2050 vision)		
Uncertainties		

5.1 What internal forces could **SUPPORT** or **ACCELERATE** progress?

5.2 What external forces could **SUPPORT** or **ACCELERATE** progress toward achieving the desired future for the year 2050?

5.3 What internal forces could **HINDER** or **SLOW DOWN** progress? (e.g., youth migration, lack of return)

5.4 What external forces could **HINDER** or **SLOW DOWN** progress?

5.5 What internal or external **UNCERTAINTIES** could hinder or slow down progress?

PART 6 – ACTION PLAN AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This is a policy recommendation phase. This phase identifies the necessary conditions to achieve the desired future by 2050. Here, we move from analysis to concrete action. The questions focus on what we need to do to reach the 2050 vision. The purpose of this section is to establish a clear, realistic, and actionable plan to achieve the stated objectives, with a focus on policies and partnerships.

6.1 Who do you need to collaborate with to achieve the 2050 vision? Why?

6.2 What resources or conditions must be in place to reach the 2050 vision? What potential barriers or constraints could block the achievement of these objectives?

PART 7 – COMMUNICATION AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

7.1 What stories or messages inspire you to get involved?

7.2 What tools (e.g., short films, school activities) could help spread the 2050 vision?

7.3 Who are the most credible messengers?

PART 8 – MONITORING AND FEEDBACK MECHANISMS

8.1 What indicators show us that we are on the right track from one stage to the next? Reflect on the three previous stages (2026–2030; 2031-2040; 2041-2050).

8.2 What mechanisms can help us refine and adjust this vision as uncertainties emerge?

(e.g., A mixed group – e.g., community leaders, youth, women, farmers, experts – that oversees the vision; Holding annual or biennial meetings with key stakeholders – community members, authorities, NGOs, experts)

8.3 Do you believe that the future you envision for 2050 can become reality? What are the chances it will happen?

Estimate the probability: x%

8.4. Now, in the end, without thinking about what you wish would happen, what is, in your opinion, the most likely scenario for the year 2050? What do you think the Târnava Mare microregion will look like in that year? And why?

End of the session and goodbye

“Thank you” from the workshop facilitators, and final thoughts from the participants.